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HARMONY OF MOTHERLAND AND MOTHER IMAGES IN POETRY

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Abstract. *In poetry, the image of the mother is reflected in the artistic whole with the concept of homeland. The issue of poetic harmony of the concept of mother and homeland. This article is analyzed on the example of the poetry of Abdulla Oripov, Amon Matjon, Khurshid Davron.*

Keywords. *Artistic integrity and generalized image, image and imagery, poetic image, lyrical character, love.*

An artistic image, a universe that embodies objective and subjective beginnings, reflects the creator's personality along with real reality. Therefore, each poem is a world, a product of the creator's imaginative thinking. An image that is a product of artistic thinking is defined as istilah as follows. A reflection of existence seen by an artist's eye and creatively processed on an ideal basis, expressed in a form that can be emotionally perceived [2.19]. The image, as a reworked unit of poetry, combines intelligence and feeling. According to the esoteric foundations of knowledge of the world, the original artistry belongs to Allah, the absolute power that created the Pen in the Muslim East, who, as the only and absolute creator, created man on his basis. The word was originally in God as a great weapon that created the world from nothing. Boundless worlds were created by a single command of the Creator. This endless weapon made man the dearest of all creatures in existence as a symbol of his power to create and destroy, to cause happiness and unhappiness. When the power of words, the power of the pen and the artistic thinking of the creative soul unite, an artistic image is born [3.72]. There are perfect creators who have the skill of creating a philosophical lyrical image, who can connect with

the divine spirit, there are writers who have broken through the layers of imagination of the human mind. Abdulla Oripov is one of such wise poets in Uzbek literature who has a unique style of image creation [2.35]. In the article, we will consider Abdulla Oripov's unique image of the mother, the combination of magnificent poetic images, common images of motherland and motherland. Looking at Abdulla Oripov's work, we notice that he often refers to the image of his mother. His poems include "Mother", "Letter to my mother", "Uzbek mother", "Ayol madhi", "The name mother", "Remembering my mother", "Childhood years", "Mother's mother", "To my mother's death". rs can be a vivid example of this. In some of Abdulla Oripov's poems dedicated to the image of the mother, the comparison of the mother to the motherland evokes new poetic thoughts and certain aesthetic feelings. To create such cast lines, every word should feel poetic [6.95]. In the poetry of Abdulla Oripov and the skill of image creation, we can see the love of Navoiyvor's wisdom. During the million-year life of the son of man on earth, the experiences of the ancestors created the most diverse forms of life on the planet. Based on these life experiences, a person has improved. Scholars write interesting opinions about people.

According to Farobi, according to his nature, a person needs other people to organize, strengthen and improve his life. According to Ibn Sina, man differs from all other animals in his language, intelligence and thinking. Although man is an incredibly perfect being, he is usually weaker than other creatures in nature at the time of his first birth. In the Qur'an, the concept of weakness in relation to man is mentioned 52 times in 45 verses. He will need a mother who surrounds him with strength and talent. As stated by Ibn Sina, the language elevates a person to the quality of a living creature. The word, the great weapon that created the world from nothing, is imprinted on the mind, heart, and tongue by the mother for the first time. Therefore, the name of the language is the mother tongue. Motherland is the name of the soil on which man first stepped. Because of this, there is no artist who does

not honor his motherland and mother. The feeling of homeland is a feeling encoded in the human mind from the mother's womb. As long as a person lives, this feeling grows, grows, and develops like his age. In the poetry of the wise poet Abdulla Oripov, we observe a harmonious image of the images of Motherland and Motherland. The poem called "The Name of Mother" attracts our attention. Before analyzing the poem, it is important to pay attention to its title. In modern Uzbek literature, the practice of naming poems is quite common. The main reason for this is the need for an ideological and artistic understanding, which the title fulfills. The value of the name "Mother" is reflected in the entire idea of the poem.

The title emphasizes the image that is the basis of the topic. The main text focuses on other important aspects of the image (unity in the mother, non-repetition). The name "Mother" is connected to the name "Vatan" and "Vatan" in turn is connected to the name "Mother".

They say they are a fierce price,
Brave when he gives his life in battle,
Endure the pains and rest,
They whisper one word: Mother[1.88].

As if the poet were telling a story, as if he were telling a fairy tale, he paints a picture of the momentary moments in the mind of the reader, when the fierce Bahadurs gave their lives on the battlefields. In this moment, the reader can see the images of the hero that are not written in the poem. Of course, if the student is smart. He can bring to mind the pains, the last breaths, and the last expressions on the faces of those who are angry. This scene is characteristic of the three lines of the poem, and in the fourth line, an important emotional idea is expressed, that the word "mother" is an afterword, the hero's dream, longing, pain, and farewell words on the eve of the journey from this world to another. uses instead of . Perhaps, while saying these words, the entire life of the hero will be sealed in one moment. No matter how strong and fierce the hero is, he feels his weak and kind mother in front of him. The

last breath and the last word, "Mother." So even those who are full of strength and power worship the mother when they are weak. If a person's last word is mother, then his eternal destination will be mother earth. In fact, such great conclusions, which are beyond the text of the poem, are hidden in every word of the master and wise poet. The poet actually puts support, inexhaustible strength, love and trust under the name mother.

A great sage commented on the universe,
Finally, he recognized the country where he was born.
With respect when speaking,
Mother, he called his tongue for the first time [1.89]

In the article "The Power of the Living Word", Suvon Meli compares the importance of words in everyday life and in poetry, describing: "In poetry, the word works with all its power." The poet's skill is that he can turn simple words into great power and wise thought without excessive allusions. In the first quatrain, the sanctity of the glorified Mother, her important quality in human life is emphasized, while in the second quatrain, another lonely and unique motif is compared to language. This is the meaning that stands out in the poem. But the great sage, in the path of the past time and space in the way of interpreting the world, got to know himself and his identity, through this he got to know the country he was born in, and through mother (yes, that's how) his language, consciousness, and worldview were formed. , it is said that he called the language his mother for the first time.

Abdulla Oripov, whether he writes about nature or the image of his mother, does not avoid the topic of his motherland. It illuminates the hero's understanding of his identity in the sacred space and time. Self-awareness begins with the awareness of the mother who brought her offspring into this bright world, and through the mother with the awareness of national values: the nation, history, and the world of religion. After these realizations, he calls the language his mother, the means of

communication of people - the door to the heart. He glorifies the holy land that grew up in his bosom as his motherland.

Poets of the world for the honor of the Motherland

Adjectives are lined up and lined up,

Finally, the words have one meaning

Those who end up calling the motherland [1.89]

In the third quartet, it is the poets' turn. While poets are looking for a series of adjectives for the honor of the Motherland, they come to a conclusion on a word consisting of only three letters. Mother. We have the opportunity to observe the meaning of the word in this paragraph in two different meanings. They come to one meaningful idea. The meaning is unique, unique and unrepeatable, and they represent to the mother that the Motherland is also unique and unique. They conclude, Motherland. The image of the author is a price, he appears as a sage, a poet. Through the language of these images, the poet expresses his respect for the woman - mother, who contributed to the development of the thinking space and the human society existing in this space.

If it's good, it's worthless.

A word is colorless when repeated,

Motherland is one in this bright world.

There is only one name in the world called mother [1.89].

In the above three quatrains, the author expresses his thoughts in the language of images, and in the last quatrain, the author shows himself as a wise poet and son of the country, Abdulla Oripov. Even when it is said that it is a poem by Abdulla Oripov, the author is hidden, it will be fully visible in the conclusion. The poet shows that most of the honey is worthless and the powerful words become discolored when repeated. In order to avoid repetition, it indicates that only one word is needed as a native word. The final conclusion is that the suffix is Mother, the language is Mother's language, Motherland is Motherland, All of them are united by the unity

of one holy word mother. The poet's artistic thinking brings this real reality to the level of a poetic image.

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Groves along the coast of Sirdaryo are shrinking

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Annotation. As a result of the activities of entrepreneurs on the banks of the Syrdarya, groves are shrinking, and as a result, there is a negative impact on flora and fauna and the ecosystem. Water management structures built from the source to the confluence of the Syrdarya and their water consumption.

Key words: Syrdarya, grove, river bed, reservoir, Aral Sea.

In the process of getting to know the water resources of Tashkent region, the Syr Darya flowing through the borders of Bekobod district, where I was born and raised, attracted my attention. The image of the river that I know has changed completely over the past 25-30 years. It's no secret that as the population increases, the water in the river decreases year by year. This huge river is the longest river in Central Asia, after the Amudarya, it is the busiest river. Its length, including the Norin River, is 3020 kilometers. The Syr Darya flows through the territory of Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and is separated by a dam on the initiative of the Kazakh state in the northern part of the lake Aral, not to that drying "helpless sea" - It flows into the Small Aral. The distance from Arolboyi to Small Arol is 250 km. The importance of this river for our region cannot be expressed in words. The reason we say this is that the following most important structures are connected with

the overflowing of the river bed. Today, about 60 large and small hydroelectric stations have been built in the river bed. Large reservoirs such as Tokhtagul, Qairokum, Chordara, and the Aydar-Arnasoy lake system were formed in the Syrdarya basin. In other words, Syrdarya is the source of life for the region. In recent years, the expansion of irrigated land in Central Asia has led to a decrease in river water. Climate change and shrinking glaciers continue to cause major environmental problems in the river basin. The Syrdaryo originates from the Norin River, which flows from Central Tianshan and is formed by the confluence of the Big Norin and Little Norin Rivers. It corresponds to the territory of Tokhtagul district of Jalalabad region of the Republic of Tajikistan. These areas belong to Chuy region. Its source is the glaciers in the mountains. Tokhtagul borders Talas, Chuy and Norin regions. When the Big Norin and the Little Norin join together, they get the name Norin. Large and small rivers such as Uzun Ahmed, Karasuv, Ona Archa, Otbosh, Olabuka are added to it. The Tokhtagul reservoir is located between the Chotkal and Fergana mountain ranges. This reservoir was built in 1962-75 of the last century. Total water volume is 19.5 km³, length is 65 km, width is 12 km, depth is 215 meters. The hydro facility is designed to irrigate an area of 900,000 hectares. Currently, the volume of water is 7 km³. The reservoir is named after the famous Kyrgyz poet Tokhtagul Sotilganov. The Tokhtagul hydroelectric station was built in 1961 at the same time as the construction of the hydroelectric power station. Uchkurgon, Kuribsoy, Tokhtagul, Otboshi, Tashkomir and Shamoldisoy hydroelectric power stations were built on the Norin River. The power plant works on the water flow from the Tokhtagul reservoir. Its total capacity is 1.2 mln. 124 kW. hydroelectric plant produces an average of 5 billion kilowatt hours of electricity per year. The Norin river enters the territory of Uzbekistan from the Uchkurgan district of the Namangan region. In Uchkurgan district, water is taken from the river to the big Fergana canal. The canal is the largest hydraulic structure built in the Fergana Valley. The length of the channel is 350 km. and the water consumption is equal to 532 m³/sec. Today,

about 200,000 hectares of cultivated land in the countries of Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan are being irrigated through the Big Fergana Canal. In the village of Baliqchi of Uchkurgan district, the Norin river and the Black river join and take the name Sirdarya. The area of the river basin is approximately 462,000 km², and its main watershed is 219,000 km². The river flows through the Beshariq district of the Fergana region to the Sogd region of the Republic of Tajikistan and reaches the Qairakum reservoir. This reservoir is 55 km long and 22 km wide. Today, the water volume of the Qairakum reservoir is 3 billion 443 million m³, and the water inflow into the reservoir is 892 m³/sec. and the output of water is 880 m³/sec.

The reservoir is used to irrigate cultivated fields in Bekobod district of Tashkent region, Syrdarya and Jizzakh regions, and the neighboring Republic of Kazakhstan. The middle course of the river corresponds to the territory of Uzbekistan. "Farhod hydroelectric plant" was built on the banks of the Syrdarya in the city of Bekobod, Tashkent region, with a total capacity of 126 megawatts. It provides electrical energy to Sirdarya region, Bekobod city, Metallurgical Combine of Uzbekistan and "Bekobodcement" plant. Syrdarya flows through Syrdarya region and enters the territory of Kazakhstan. The river reaches Chordara reservoir. Chordara is the largest reservoir in the middle reaches of the Syr Darya, and the water structure was built for irrigation and energy purposes. The reservoir is located in the regions of South Kazakhstan region of the Republic of Kazakhstan and Jizzakh region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Chordara reservoir was filled with water in 1966, it is 80 km long and 25 km wide. This huge river flows through Turkestan, Kyzylorda, Baikanur regions and flows into Kichik Arol on Arolboyi. Although we cannot contribute to the increase of the river's water, we can protect the forests along the Syrdarya, its biological diversity, and reproduce and restore the flora and fauna of the forest complex. it is the duty of all of us not to interfere.

But today, the rivers, which were once rich in wildlife and fish, are in danger, and in some cases, there is a possibility that the Small Aral that are found in the middle of the riverbeds will completely disappear.

Law violations were found in 385 out of 544 enterprises surveyed during the environmental control activities conducted by the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection. 70% of violations of the law are due to unauthorized discharge of wastewater into the water body, 20% to illegal mining of sand and gravel, 5% to dumping of waste in unspecified places, and 5% to non-existence of environmental and regulatory documents. "In addition, during the raids conducted around the riverbeds, 918 cases of illegal mining of sand and gravel, dumping and burning of waste in unspecified places were detected and administrative fines of 1 billion 85 million soums were imposed. According to the relevant decision of the President, the mining of sand and gravel materials in the riverbeds will be carried out only by business entities and other organizations involved in the contract under the procedure established by the "Safe River" under the Ministry of Emergency Situations during their cleaning. That is, entrepreneurs can carry out cleaning works in riverbeds with a high risk of flooding and remove excess stones and gravel under appropriate conditions. In practice, businessmen harm the nature of the river and benefit from it.

It has long been known that a violent relationship with rivers and streams has negative consequences. Nevertheless, the topography of the river bed was disturbed as a result of mining sand-gravel mixture in an unmarked place with the equipment belonging to some enterprises. "In 93.5 percent of stone crushing and screening enterprises, there are no concrete ponds or clarifiers intended for the primary treatment of wastewater. There are cases of industrial waste water being dumped directly from the clarifier into open water bodies or the terrain. The laboratory analysis of samples taken from waste water revealed that its content was 74, 100, and 124 times higher than the established standard for solids, respectively, and

additional compensation payments were calculated for these enterprises. But the damage done to nature is huge", the official representative admitted that limiting and suspending this type of business activity will have a negative impact on construction works and cause a sharp increase in the price of gravel on the market. But this cannot be an excuse to justify the crime against nature. On September 23, Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the decision "On measures to further improve the system of protection of water bodies". According to the text of the document, special attention is being paid to the improvement of the ecological situation in the country, including the protection of water bodies, the rational use of natural resources, as well as the prevention of emergency situations in the event of floods and landslides. At the same time, there are gaps in the legislation for the cleaning of riverbeds and water protection zones, lakes, reservoirs, canals, collectors and other water bodies, as well as sand and gravel in the implementation of work to strengthen their banks. is creating conditions for unauthorized extraction of its materials.

Project documents for cleaning river beds and strengthening riverbanks should be subject to state environmental expertise by the bodies of the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection in accordance with the procedure established by law.

In conclusion, it should be said that the reason for the daily deterioration of the ecosystem is not only the inter-period water distribution conflict, but also due to the continuous quarrying of stones from the banks of the Syr Darya river, in the last 20 years, the river bed has sometimes changed depending on the location of the quarries. It is moving to the right, sometimes to the left, and is changing its course. As a result, the orchards that have existed for many years are several kilometers away from the river bank, and it is a pity that the flora and fauna are becoming scarce due to the lack of water and moisture. However, it is no secret to any of us that some animals living in these forests are included in the Red Book.

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Multispiral Computed Tomography Comparative Analysis and Justification of Chronic Lung Disease Complications in Patients with Covid-19 Pneumonia

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Abstract:

The article presents the results of computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, ultrasound, chest x-ray in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia. A comparative analysis of the diagnostic information content of each of the methods of radiological examination was carried out. It has been determined that magnetic resonance imaging and ultrasound can be used as an alternative to computed tomography.

Keywords: X-ray diagnostics, computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, radiography, ultrasound, COVID-19 pneumonia.

Introduction

Due to the high mortality from COVID-19 pneumonia, adequate and timely diagnosis comes to the fore. At the same time, radiation research methods play a huge role in identifying signs of inflammatory changes in the lungs, determining the

volume of lung damage, monitoring treatment and predicting the course of the disease. The most informative method of detecting changes in the lungs associated with COVID-19 is rightfully computed tomography of the thoracic cavity, which allows identifying typical manifestations of viral lung lesions [1,7]. However, in some cases, CT is problematic, especially in patients in the intensive care unit. In addition, due to the high radiation load, the question arises of limiting the use of this method in the framework of frequent control studies.

The purpose of the investigation. In order to reduce radiation exposure and obtain additional diagnostic information, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was used in a number of patients [8].

Radiography is significantly inferior in the sensitivity of computed tomography, it allows us to confidently detect only severe forms of pneumonia [6]. Most of the available studies indicate that traditional lung radiography has low sensitivity at an early stage. Ultrasound examination (ultrasound) of the lungs is considered as an alternative to X-ray studies [2]. Important advantages of ultrasound compared to radiography are: zero radiation load, assessment of infiltration in Live mode, the ability to monitor the dynamics of pneumonia. [3]. Demonstrating high sensitivity in the diagnosis of pneumonia, ultrasound at the same time has its limitations — sensitivity parameters are significantly reduced with a small lesion of lung tissue, localization of pneumonia in areas difficult to reach for the ultrasound wave [3, 5]. In this regard, ultrasound in the diagnosis of coronavirus pneumonia requires a more detailed study.

Materials and methods

The clinical and radiation data of 27 patients (15 women and 12 men) who underwent COVID-19 and were observed in medical and preventive institutions of the city of Karaganda, Temirtau from August 2020 to December 2021 were

analyzed. The average age of patients was 37.2 ± 15.7 years. All patients underwent high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT), which was performed with a thin slice of 1-2 mm at the inhalation delay in the pulmonary and mediastinal modes with a scanning area from the tops of the lungs to the sinuses, in the native mode on devices with 128 slices. Scanning was carried out on a GE Optima CT 660 computed tomograph

The consequence of the high density of recording for CT studies, as well as the temporary technical malfunction of CT machines caused by the increased round-the-clock load on X-ray tubes, was the inability to perform CT in some patients. It is in such a situation of lack of opportunities that magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has become an alternative method of diagnosing pulmonary changes.

MRI examination of the chest organs was carried out in 9 patients on Toshiba Titan Vantage 1.5 T MRI scanners (Canon Medical), in T1-, T2-weighted modes (T1VI, T2VI), STIR-modes, in axial and frontal planes, with breath retention.

Radiography was performed in straight posterior and lateral projections, when the patient's condition allowed him to be in a vertical position, whereas in a straight anterior projection — with the patient's horizontal position. During X-ray examination, pneumonia was confirmed or excluded, the extent of darkening was estimated depending on the localization by segments, the presence of complications in the form of destructive processes, pleural effusion.

Ultrasound examination of the lungs was performed on a Toshiba AplioMX ultrasound machine using a 5 MHz convexic sensor.

Ultrasound assessed the localization of the process, the length of the infiltration site, as well as the number of B-lines and "air bronchograms" per unit area.

Radiation diagnostic methods were used strictly according to the indications and prescription of the attending physician, and patients or their legal representatives

signed an informed consent to conduct the study. Results and discussion. Computed tomography.

The most common symptom of COVID-19- pneumonia at the initial stage of development is called a "matte spot" [1,7,9,10,11,12]. This sign is morphologically represented by a compaction of the parenchyma of the organ with partial preservation of pneumatization, due to which bronchial and vascular structures are observed (Fig 1a). The symptom was detected in all patients.

The second most frequent pattern was the consolidation of lung tissue (reticular intra-lobular striation), it was observed in 15 patients (55%). In the images, consolidation is characterized by a pronounced increase in parenchymal density, against which the bronchial structures and vessels do not differ in comparison with the affected area.

The symptom of "cobblestone pavement" ("patchwork quilt") is a combination of changes in the type of "frosted glass" and pronounced thickening of interstitial intra- and inter-lobular partitions (Fig. 2b). This CT pattern was found in 8 patients (about 30%).

Magnetic resonance imaging

The MRI study of OGK was performed on 9 patients on Toshiba MRI scanners in a 1.5- Ton Titanium in T1-, T2-weighted modes (T1VI, T2VI), with respiratory delay. The results of MRI and CT studies of OGK were compared.

The results obtained indicate a high sensitivity of T2-VI in detecting consolidation zones and "frosted glass", with comparable diagnostic value with high-resolution computed tomography data. This is due to the high intensity of the signal in tissues with an increased fluid content (inflammation or edema), both in the alveolar and interstitial spaces.

Ultrasound diagnostics

According to the Russian government, infection due to panic attacks related to COVID- 19 caused increased sensitivity [2,3,5].

Ultrasound signs of the lungs are normally: hyperechoic smooth pleural line, sliding of the visceral pleura (the so-called sign of the "seashore"), A-lines, single B-lines (less than four in one intercostal space).

With ultrasound of the lungs and pleural cavity, the detected signs corresponded to the signs of CT. The use of a lung pair of the "frosted glass" type, manifested in the fact that the ultrasound corresponded to multihocal, discrete/merging B-lines.

All patients with confirmed COVID-19 pneumonia on CT OGK had echo signs of interstitial changes in lung parenchyma: multiple (narrow) B-lines, merging (wide) B- lines, as well as areas of subpleural consolidation and the so-called "white lung".

The symptom of "cobblestone pavement" in ultrasound of the lungs is characterized by a combination of B-lines interspersed with unexpressed subpleural consolidation in places of thickening of the septa and alveolar lesions. An important limitation of the method is the lack of visualization of deeply located structures of lung tissue. Visualization of such areas was possible only with a significant loss of airiness of subpleural areas, for example, during their consolidation. At the same time, only those consolidation zones that are located closer to the pleura are available.

Radiography

The importance of radiography is due to the fact that, due to its availability, it is often the primary, and sometimes the only method used to visualize changes in the lungs when coronavirus pneumonia is suspected in small towns, regional centers of our country. When X-ray diagnostics of coronavirus pneumonia for the correct interpretation of images, it is recommended to pay attention to the following:

- 1) at the onset of the disease, the radiograph shows an increase in the pulmonary pattern of a heavy type due to thickening and compaction, and later swelling of the walls of the bronchi and their stroma in the basal, basal sections and often on the periphery along the costal surfaces. Perhaps you have a suspicion of COVID-19, which may not be recognized, because it is possible to recognize a genetic virus;
- 2) after 7-10 days from the beginning of clinical manifestations, extensive areas of fine- mesh pattern enhancement appear with a decrease in the airiness of the lung tissue, up to the "frosted glass" pattern;
- 3) after a few more days, infiltrates from inhomogeneous medium to homogeneous high intensity appear mainly in the peripheral parts, located along the costal surface.

The correct interpretation of radiographs in patients with coronavirus pneumonia is more difficult in comparison with CT, MRI or even ultrasound. Therefore, if there is a suspicion of the coronavirus nature of pneumonia detected by radiography, it is necessary to prescribe a CT scan.

Conclusions. Computed tomography, of course, is taken into account by the modern method of diagnosing lung infection COVID-19-pneumonia. The presented observations illustrate the diversity of the CT picture of coronavirus pneumonia detected during the initial examination of patients. The sensitivity of the MRI method in assessing inflammatory changes in the lungs in COVID-19 is inferior to CT, however, to identify the main symptoms (an increase in the density of the parenchyma by the type of "frosted glass" and consolidation), it may be a very real alternative in the absence of the possibility of performing CT.

In the conditions of a pandemic and mass admission of patients, lung ultrasound can be very useful, as well as in the absence of a CT scanner, in an intensive care unit, for "bedside" diagnostics. X-ray examination of OGK is not the method of choice for the diagnosis of COVID-19, it is used in patients in intensive care and intensive

care units when CT is impossible. The low sensitivity of lung radiography in the early stages is explained by the fact that the initial manifestations of coronavirus pneumonia are areas of "frosted glass" type compaction, the visualization of which in most cases lies beyond the diagnostic capabilities of radiography.

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THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INTERNAL ANTI-CORRUPTION MEASURES IN THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION OFFENSES

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Abstract. The article describes the role and significance of internal anti-corruption measures in the prevention of corruption offenses. In particular, the relevance and importance of taking effective measures in view of the number and volume of corruption offenses, as well as some features of the issues, the lack of clear regulation of internal procedures that need to be identified and measures taken to address them are indicated. The study provides a causal method for analyzing the issue of effective regulation of legal relations, that is, the sufficiency of control measures, compliance with established norms, which are aimed at the effectiveness of anti-corruption measures and ensuring the development of a society without corruption. The system of measures to prevent corruption provided for in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" is analyzed. Anti-corruption measures is not effective, and sometimes exacerbates the position of state bodies in front of the public. In this regard, the assessment of corruption risks arising from the implementation of the assigned tasks and functions, which must be formed on the basis of internal and external sources, is of particular importance.

Key words: corruption offenses, legal relations, monitoring of possible risks, measures to prevent corruption, anti-corruption programs of government agencies.

Introduction

During the implementation of in-depth reforms in various sectors of the country's life, the issue of establishing and applying effective anti-corruption measures by state bodies remains relevant. Since the object of corruption offenses are public relations that arise between individuals (legal entities) persons and organizations, represented by public officials.

At the moment, the legislation does not clearly distinguish between them, but does not exclude their presence either. This circumstance begins and ends in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Corruption” (Adolat, 2017), which defines corruption as the illegal use by a person of his official or official position in order to obtain material or non-material benefits in his personal interests or in the interests of other persons, as well as the illegal provision of such benefits.

Theoretical and practical framework

According to M. Weber, power is the ability to carry out one's own will even in spite of resistance (Weber, 1990). In other words, non-compliance with the established norms of behavior in society by a person who has authority in order to obtain an unlawful advantage for himself or in the interests of third parties. This circumstance indicates that the list of corruption offenses cannot be exhaustive and clearly fixed. But, nevertheless, it is important to indicate which corruption torts should be

qualified as criminally punishable acts, administratively punishable violations, and maybe even civil, disciplinary or even ethical offenses.

At the same time, it should also be noted the assessment of international experts of the OECD, whose analysis is based on the study of 13 types of crimes provided for by the Criminal Code (Art. 167, 168, 192-9, 192-10, 192- 11, 205, 206, 211, 212, 213, 214, 243) (OECD, 2019). Which, in turn, argues that today the legislation defines corruption crimes, and not corruption offenses, although the Law “On Combating Corruption” determines that a corruption offense is an act that has signs of corruption, for which the legislation provides for liability. In this regard, the question arises in which actions or events a person, by virtue of his official or official position, violates the established norms in order to obtain material or non-material benefits in his personal interests or in the interests of other persons, as well as illegally provides such benefits.. The study of this issue has shown that without a clear and transparent regulation of these two elements, which are an integral part of the legal fact and, consequently, the very meaning of the legal relationship, it is not possible to minimize corruption risks or even eliminate .

This leads to the paradox of how effectively the legal relationship is regulated: Are there sufficient control measures? Are the established norms observed or are there gaps in them? All this leads to the fact that state bodies and other organizations must take measures that would answer the above questions and, as a result, would serve to establish anti-corruption measures and ensure the development of a society without corruption.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated May 27, 2019 No.DP–5729 (Adolat, 2019), it is determined that the primary task of the heads of state bodies and organizations is to eliminate the causes and conditions that contribute to corruption in the relevant area. offences,

through the implementation of effective internal anti-corruption measures, the introduction of mechanisms for accountability and openness of their activities, practical measures to ensure compliance with ethical rules and prevent conflicts of interest. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Corruption”, the system of measures to prevent corruption includes:

1. Measures to prevent corruption in public administration.
2. Measures to prevent corruption in the field of socio-economic development and entrepreneurship.
3. Measures to prevent and resolve conflicts of interest.
4. Measures to prevent corruption in the field of administrative procedures.
5. Measures to prevent corruption in the field of public procurement.
6. Anti-corruption expertise of legal acts and their projects.

Internal anti-corruption measures

In international practice, there are different approaches to the definition of a system for the prevention of corruption. For example, the anti-corruption system in the Netherlands includes, inter alia, the following key procedural and institutional measures:

- a system for monitoring the possible risks of corruption in state and public organizations and strict control over the activities of persons at risk;
- a system of punishments for corruption, with the main measure being the prohibition to work in state organizations and the loss of all social benefits provided by the public service;

- a system of rewarding positive actions of officials, aimed at ensuring that it is beneficial for an official both materially and morally to behave honestly and efficiently;

– A state security system to combat corruption has been created, such as a special police force with significant powers to detect cases of corruption. Similar measures are also applied in Israel and Canada.

Other countries also practice successful anti-corruption measures. In particular, civil society, as an institution inherent in a democratic regime, can increase the effectiveness of the activities of independent anti-corruption commissions. Successfully similar bodies function in Hong Kong, Singapore, Malaysia, Taiwan .

Analyze of the internal anti-corruption measures

In this regard, today the issue of developing effective internal anti-corruption programs is acute, since, according to public opinion polls conducted by the Izhtimoiy Fikr Center from 2016 to 2018, the level of corruption and bribery in some areas has increased several times. For example, according to citizens in the field of healthcare and medicine, corruption has doubled over 3 years (in 2016 - 26.1%, in 2017 - 37.6%, in 2018 - 43.7%). In the field of education, 34.3% of citizens who considered corruption in 2016 changed their minds to 39.4% in 2018, and in the tax sector there was an increase from 7% to 12.2%.

According to the results of the public opinion poll "Fighting Corruption in the Mirror of Public Opinion", conducted by the above-mentioned center, healthcare, the system of higher and public education are identified as areas subject to corruption, followed by courts, prosecutor's offices, internal affairs bodies, tax authorities and authorities. sanitary and epidemiological supervision and control (OECD, 2019).

For example, In 2021, 3,769 criminal cases of corruption against 5,483 people across the country were sent to the courts for consideration. Compared to 2020, the number of criminal cases sent to court increased by 2,621, and the number of persons prosecuted increased by 3,760, or 218 percent.

In 2020, as a result of corruption-related crimes, the state and society suffered material damage in the amount of 500 billion 102 million soums, of which 355 billion soums or 71 percent reimbursed. And in 2021, the amount of material damage amounted to 1 trillion 282 billion soums, of which 887 billion soums or 69.1 percent reimbursed.

For internal management of corruption risks, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 6, 2021 No. 5177, state bodies and entities with a state share in the authorized capital, including banks, are obliged to implement and effectively operate the internal anti-corruption control system.

To date, the Internal Anti-Corruption Control Units operate in 88 government agencies, the work of 52 of which is not fully established.

At the same time, the Anti-Corruption Agency studied and analyzed the observance by local authorities of their obligations to post socially significant information on the official website and other information resources.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that the internal measures taken to combat corruption are not effective, and sometimes exacerbate the position of state bodies in front of the public. In this regard, the assessment of corruption risks arising from the implementation of the assigned tasks and functions, which must be formed on the basis of internal and external sources, is of particular importance:

regulatory legal acts and internal acts of state bodies regulating the implementation of functions for which corruption risks are assessed (for example, regulations on structural divisions, job descriptions of employees, etc.);

materials of internal audits, including internal audits;

the results of the meetings of the Ethics Commission;

reports on the facts of inducing an employee to commit corruption offenses;

results of a survey of stakeholders, recipients of public services, experts, representatives of civil society institutions and other interested parties, including sociological research;

statistical data on offenses in the field of activity of the state body;

appeals of citizens and legal entities to communication channels intended for reporting information about corrupt practices;

appeals of civil society institutions and information in the media containing information about corruption offenses or facts of non-compliance by employees of state bodies with the rules of ethical behavior;

comments on social networks;

results of anti-corruption monitoring of internal anti-corruption programs;

materials submitted by law enforcement agencies, including acts of prosecutorial response, materials on criminal cases and others.

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**Professional ethics of a lawyer and its social significance
in the Republic of Uzbekistan**

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ABSTRACT:

Modern advocacy plays a significant role in the system of government as it establishes and sustains specific connections between lawyers and ordinary people. The text highlights the pivotal role of lawyers in protecting human rights and interests, stressing the need for high standards of professionalism and ethics. It discusses the importance of legal ethics in ensuring fairness, legality, and morality in professional conduct, regulated by laws and codes of conduct. Additionally, it emphasizes the moral responsibility of lawyers to maintain integrity and dignity, even in challenging situations, to uphold public trust in the legal profession. Overall, it underscores the critical significance of ethical behavior in legal practice for preserving the profession's integrity and societal trust.

Keywords: Lawyer, law, social, professional, behavior, Decree, legal, rules, human, ethics, principles, the Chamber of Advocates, freedom, honor, rights, dignity,

protection, competence, client, self-justification, independence, standards, skills, duties, reforms, society, culture, the Code, grievance.

"I'd like to serve, but not to be a servant!"

A.S. Griboyedov, "Woe from Wi.

The profession of a lawyer is directly related to the protection of human interests, such as rights, freedoms, honor and dignity, and to a large extent determines the fate of a person. For this reason, the legal profession, along with other professions such as doctors, teachers, judges, prosecutors and others, which also aim to assist and protect human beings (including their life, health, education, and rights and freedoms), are held to their own high standards of professionalism, ethics and fairness. These principles underpin their legal defense and legal aid activities.

The purpose of professional ethics, as in any field, including the legal profession, is to ensure that high standards of behavior, principles of fairness, legality and morality are observed in professional activities [1].

In accordance with the requirements set out in the Laws "On the Advocacy" and "On Guarantees of Advocacy and Social Protection of Advocates", lawyers of the Republic of Uzbekistan have certain rights and duties, and enjoy the protection of laws that ensure the independence and inviolability of their professional activities. In addition to these Laws, a Presidential Decree was signed on 12 May 2018, aimed at radically improving the effectiveness of the institution of the Bar and expanding the independence of lawyers [2]. The Decree notes the significant work carried out in recent years in the country aimed at enhancing the role and significance of the Bar as one of the key instruments for the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals and legal entities in the context of judicial and legal reforms[3].

The Institute of Advocacy, being aware of its moral responsibility to society, carries out its activities on the basis of the Rules of Professional Ethics of Advocates, which was promulgated on 27.09.2013 by the II Conference of the Chamber of Advocates of the Republic of Uzbekistan [4]. Thus, legal ethics is a scientific direction that analyses the requirements for moral and ethical qualities necessary for employees of the legal sphere, in addition, studies the features of the culture of legal activity. The professional activities of a judge, prosecutor, investigator are characterized by their peculiarities and direct impact on the rights and interests of people, which highlights the importance of identifying and assessing the moral content of their work [5]. In addition, the duties and rights of lawyers are also regulated in other legislation, including the Code of Criminal Procedure, the Code of Civil Procedure, the Code of Economic Procedure and other similar documents.

This set of Rules includes the principles of honesty, confidentiality, dedication to the client's interests, competence, as well as compliance with laws and professional standards. Such rules define the immutable rules of behavior and relations with both clients and colleagues, as well as establish requirements for the quality of services provided by lawyers. Moreover, a lawyer must maintain an appropriate demeanor and dress code that meets all the requirements of business standards. Continuous improvement of his/her knowledge and professional skills is also an important part of his/her duties. Compliance with these Rules helps to maintain public confidence in the legal profession and ensure effective protection of the rights and interests of clients.

Another important principle is the observance of the advocate's secrecy, which is understood as "all information related to the provision of legal assistance by an advocate to his/her client". The law prohibits an advocate from disclosing information provided by a client in connection with the provision of legal assistance without the client's consent. A lawyer is bound by ethical and legal principles of confidentiality: he/she cannot be called and questioned as a witness regarding

information obtained by him/her in the course of providing legal assistance or as a consequence thereof [6].

Ethical principles become a reliable guide for lawyers in making decisions in a variety of situations, including specific issues, problems, and behavioral strategies for both themselves and their clients. These principles are particularly important because it is impossible to anticipate all possible cases in advance. Nevertheless, in every situation, a lawyer should justify his/her actions to himself/herself, clients, the state, society, colleagues and his/her profession, demonstrating a high level of professionalism and ethics.

The introductory statement placed at the beginning of this research paper is a famous phrase of A.S. Griboyedov from the work "Woe from Wit". This quote has been carefully chosen to establish relevance to the research topic. In a number of cases, a lawyer's behavior towards his client should always be of a high standard, regardless of the surrounding circumstances [7]. Even if the client unfairly accuses the lawyer of incompetence or lack of commitment to the case, the lawyer must remain discreet and respectful, explaining his or her point of view to the client and explaining in detail the reasons for his or her actions or inactions that caused the grievance. At the same time, it is important that the lawyer's explanations do not sound like excuses or contain elements of self-justification, especially when the lawyer is sure of the correctness of his actions.

According to generally accepted rules, advocates are subject to disciplinary measures, such as reprimands or warnings, for breaches of professional standards. In case of a serious or systematic violation of the legislation or ethical norms governing the practice of law, an advocate's license may be revoked [8]. In deciding whether to impose disciplinary measures, the Chamber of Advocates may take into account a variety of factors, including the absence of previous offences, the existence of rewards, admissions of guilt and attempts to remedy the situation [9]. At the same

time, factors such as health status, the presence of minor dependent children, financial obligations or specialization in a particular area of law are not taken into account when deciding whether to hold an advocate liable [10].

In conclusion, it should be stressed that advocates must always preserve the honor and dignity inherent in their profession, regardless of the circumstances. The obligation to comply with the rules of advocate's ethics arises from the attribution of advocate's status. If issues of advocate's professional ethics are not regulated by legislation, an advocate must follow the customs and traditions established in the legal profession that correspond to generally accepted moral principles in society.

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Qandli diabetda gipoglekimiyaning oldini olish chora tadbirlari.

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Annotatsiya: Giperglikemiya – bu plazmadagi glyukoza konsentratsiyasining 6,1 mmol / l dan oshishi. Ushbu holatning sabablari stress, yuqori uglevodli dieta, dori-darmonlar, endokrin tizim va ichki organlarning kasalliklari bo'lishi mumkin. Asosiy klinik ko'rinishlar orasida og'iz qurishi , ko'p siyish va mushaklar kuchsizligi mavjud. Glikemiya darajasi ovqatdan va dori-darmonlardan oldin venoz yoki kapillyar qon bilan tekshiriladi. Qon shakar darajasini normallashtirish uchun parhez, dori-darmonlar (insulin, gipoglekemik vositalar) va asosiy kasallikni davolash qo'llaniladi. Ushbu maqola qandli diabetda gipoglekimiya ning oldini olish chora tadbirlari haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: gipoglekimiya, Qandli diabet, chora tadbirlar, davolash, oldini olish.

Резюме: Гипергликемия – это повышение концентрации глюкозы в плазме выше 6,1 ммоль/л. Причинами такого состояния могут быть стресс, высокоуглеводная диета, прием лекарств, заболевания эндокринной системы и внутренних органов. К основным клиническим проявлениям относятся сухость во рту, частое мочеиспускание и мышечная слабость. Уровень гликемии проверяют по венозной или капиллярной крови перед едой и

приемом лекарств. Для нормализации уровня сахара в крови применяют диету, лекарственные препараты (инсулин, сахароснижающие средства) и лечение основного заболевания. В данной статье написано о мерах профилактики гипогликемии при сахарном диабете.

Ключевые слова: гипогликемия, сахарный диабет, меры, лечение, профилактика.

Summary: Hyperglycemia is an increase in plasma glucose concentration above 6.1 mmol/l. The causes of this condition may be stress, a high-carbohydrate diet, medication, diseases of the endocrine system and internal organs. The main clinical manifestations include dry mouth, frequent urination and muscle weakness. The glycemic level is checked by venous or capillary blood before eating and taking medications. To normalize blood sugar levels, diet, medications (insulin, hypoglycemic agents) and treatment of the underlying disease are used. This article describes measures to prevent hypoglycemia in diabetes mellitus.

Key words: hypoglycemia, diabetes mellitus, measures, treatment, prevention.

Homiladorlik davrida, biokimyoviy testni o'tkazish arafasida uglevod o'z ichiga olgan ovqatni iste'mol qilishda qon shakarining qisqa muddatli o'sishi kuzatilishi mumkin. Stress ostida giperglikemiya simpato-adrenal va gipotalamo-gipofiz-adrenal tizimlarning faollashishi va kontrainsulyar gormonlar ishlab chiqarilishi tufayli yuzaga keladi. Bunday sharoitlarda giperglikemiya vaqtinchalik (qaytariladigan) bo'lib, hech qanday aralashuvni talab qilmaydi.

Qandli diabetda

Qandli diabet (QD) yuqori qon glyukoza darajasining asosiy sababidir. Qandli diabetning turli turlarida giperglikemiya rivojlanishining patogenetik mexanizmlari biroz farq qiladi. 1-toifa diabet me'da osti bezi Langergans orolchalarining beta hujayralari tomonidan insulin ishlab chiqarishning pasayishi (mutlaq insulin

yetishmovchiligi) bilan tavsiflanadi, bu esa glyukozadan periferik to'qimalar (yog ' , mushak) tomonidan energiya substrati sifatida foydalanishning buzilishiga olib keladi va shunga mos ravishda uning qonda saqlanishi ham buziladi.

2-toifa diabetda, aksincha, uzoq muddatli giperinsulinemiya tufayli mushak va yog 'to'qimalari hujayralari yuzasida insulin retseptorlari sonining kamayishi (nisbiy insulin yetishmovchiligi) tufayli insulin qarshiligi (insulinga sezgirlik chegarasining oshishi) yuzaga keladi. Gestatsion qandli diabetda (GQD) insulin klirensining pasayishi, shuningdek, fetoplasental gormonlar (platsenta laktogeni, progesteron) ta'siridan kelib chiqadi.

1-toifa diabet. Giperglikemiyaning spazmodik tabiati xarakterlidir. Qon shakar darajasining keskin o'sishi kasallikning klinik ko'rinishi paytida ham, ko'pincha dozaga rioya qilinmasa yoki insulin in'ektsiyasini o'tkazib yuborsa sodir bo'lishi mumkin. Glyukozani normal chegaralarda ushlab turish uchun umrbod insulin terapiyasi talab qilinadi.

2-toifa diabet. Bu glyukoza konsentratsiyasining sekin va barqaror o'sishi bilan tavsiflanadi, shuning uchun u juda yuqori qiymatlarga (30-40 mmol / l) ko'tarilishi mumkin. Glikemiya darajasi dietaning ta'siri ostida va antigiperglikemik dorilarni qabul qilishda pasayadi. Oshiqcha tana vaznini yo'qotish va bariatrik jarrohlik kasallikni davolashga bo'lgan ehtiyojni kamaytirishi yoki yo'q qilishi mumkin.

GQD. Homiladorlik qandli diabet bilan homiladorlikning II-III trimestrlarida qonda shakar asta-sekin ko'tariladi. Maxsus davolash tug'ruq yoki jarrohlik tug'ilish boshlanishidan oldin amalga oshiriladi. Tug'ruqdan keyingi davrda spontan remissiya tez-tez kuzatiladi, ammo 2-toifa diabetga o'tish bilan giperglikemiya davom etishi mumkin.

Boshqa endokrin buzilishlar

Qandli diabetdan tashqari, endokrin tizimning boshqa kasalliklari ham giperglikemiyaga olib kelishi mumkin. Bu asosan endokrinopatiyalarga taalluqlidir, bu esa kontrainsulyar gormonlar ishlab chiqarishning ko'payishi bilan birga keladi, ya'ni. uglevod almashinuvining turli bosqichlariga ta'sir qilish orqali glyukoza konsentratsiyasini oshiradigan gormonlar:

Tirotoksikoz. Diffuz toksik buqoq yoki toksik adenoma bilan qalqonsimon bez gormonlari glikogenolizni, glyukoneogenezni faollashtiradi va ichakda glyukoza so'rilishini rag'batlantiradi. O'rtacha giperglikemiya qalqonsimon gormonlar darajasini normallashtirishdan keyin yo'qoladi.

Giperkortizolizm. Glyukokortikosteroidlar (kortizol) glyukoneogenezni kuchaytiradi va glyukoza parchalanishini ingibitsa qiladi. Itsenko-Kushing kasalligi / sindromi bo'lsa, ko'pincha «steroid diabet» deb ataladigan kasallik rivojlanadi.

Feoxromotsitoma. Katexolaminlar (adrenalin, noradrenalin) jigarda glikogenning parchalanishini rag'batlantiradi. Giperglikemiya paroksizmal tarzda davom etadi, glyukoza darajasi simpato-adrenal inqiroz davrida keskin oshadi. Hurujlar orasida glikemiya normal chegaralarda qoladi.

Akromegaliya. Somatotropinoma gipofiz o'smasi tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan o'sish gormoni, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri giperglikemik ta'sirga qo'shimcha ravishda, periferik to'qimalar tomonidan glyukozadan foydalanishni bloklaydi, ya'ni. insulin qarshiligini hosil qiladi. Shuning uchun akromegaliya bilan giperglikemiya alohida xususiyatga ega. Glyukoza bardoshlilikining buzilishi tez-tez uchraydigan boshqa endokrinopatiyalardan farqli o'laroq, akromegaliya ko'pincha 2-toifa diabetning rivojlanishiga olib keladi.

Glyukagonoma. Glyukagon, asosiy insulin antagonisti sifatida, jigarda aminokislotalardan glyukoza hosil bo'lishini rag'batlantiradi. Giperglikemiya yengil. Ko'pgina hollarda, qon shakarini normallashtirish uchun dietani o'zgartirish kifoya qiladi.

Boshqa sabablar

Konvulsiv holatlar.

Markaziy asab tizimining organik shikastlanishlari: ensefalit, miya shishi, IV qorinchada qon ketishi.

Jigar yetishmovchiligi.

Oshqozon osti bezining og'ir kasalliklari: oshqozon osti bezi nekrozi, kistasi, fibrozi.

Dori-darmonlarni qabul qilish: tiazidli diuretiklar, glyukokortikosteroidlar, beta-adrenergik retseptorlari blokerlari.

Jiddiy somatik kasalliklar: sepsis, keng kuyishlar.

Autoimmun poliglandular sindromlar: Shmidt sindromi.

Kamdan kam uchraydigan irsiy sindromlar: Sype-Lawrence lipodistrofiyasi, Prader-Villi sindromi, Wiedemann-Beckwith sindromi.

OIV infeksiyasi.

Tashxislash

Asosan, giperglikemiya profilaktik yoki maqsadli laboratoriya qon shakarini tekshirish paytida aniqlanadi. Shu bilan birga, portativ qon glyukoza o'lchagichi bo'lgan bemorlar ertalab och qoringa glyukoza miqdorining muntazam o'sishini mustaqil ravishda aniqlashlari mumkin. Bunday holda siz darhol umumiy amaliyot shifokori yoki endokrinologga tashrif buyurishingiz kerak. Kelajakda patologik jarayonning tabiatini aniqlash uchun quyidagilarni amalga oshirish mumkin:

Uglevod almashinuvini tadqiq qilish. Giperglikemiya bilan og'rigan bemor shakar uchun siydik sinovidan o'tadi, og'iz orqali glyukoza bardoshlik testini o'tkazadi va glikemik profilning kunlik monitoringini o'tkazadi. Glyukoza testlari bilan

birgalikda ko'pincha glyukozalangan gemoglobin, qon insulini va HOMA indeksini (insulin qarshiligi) aniqlash uchun qo'shimcha ravishda tayinlanadi.

Gormonal tadqiqotlar. Agar endokrin tizim patologiyasiga shubha tug'lsa, qalqonsimon bez gormonlari (TTG, erkin T4, T3), insulinga o'xshash o'sish omili-1 va kundalik siydikda metanefrin darajasini o'lchash uchun qon tekshiruvi o'tkaziladi. Agar bemorda giperkortizolizmning klinik belgilari bo'lsa, kichik va katta deksametazon testlarini o'tkazgandan so'ng, tupurikda, shuningdek plazmadagi kortizol kontsentratsiyasini o'lchanadi.

Ultratovush. Pankreatogen kelib chiqadigan giperglikemiya bo'lsa, qorin bo'shlig'i organlarining ultratovush tekshiruvda oshqozon osti bezining exogen zichligi pasayganligi, uning shishishi, loyqa konturlar, kistalar mavjudligi va boshqalar aniqlanadi. Gipertiroidizm da qalqonsimon bezning ultratovush tekshiruvda parenxima exogenligi kamayganligini, tugunlarning mavjudligini ko'rsatadi.

KT. Buyrak usti korteksining gormonlarining yuqori ishlab chiqarilishini laboratoriya tasdiqlagan holda, buyrak usti bezlarining KT o'simta shakllanishi – kortikosteromalarni izlash uchun o'tkaziladi.

MRT. Akromegaliya va Itsenko-Kushing kasalligi bilan miyaning MRTda gipofiz bezining yaxshi sifatli o'smasi – adenoma qayd etiladi.

Uzoq muddatli giperglikemiyaning o'zi butun inson tanasiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadiganligi sababli, agar u aniqlansa, ayniqsa qon shakarini takroriy o'lchashdan so'ng, maqsadli organlarning holatini baholash uchun tekshiruv buyuriladi, unga quyidagilar kiradi:

umumiy xolesterin va lipid profilini o'rganish;

qon bosimini o'lchash;

elektrokardiogramma olish;

qon zardobida kreatinin, karbamid, siydikda – umumiy oqsil, albumin-kreatinin nisbati darajasini aniqlash, agar kerak bo'lsa, glomerulyar filtratsiya tezligini hisoblash amalga oshiriladi;

ko'z tubi tekshiruvi.

Korreksiya

Dorilar bilan davolash

Glyukoza me'yoridan ortiq bo'lgan testlarni olgandan so'ng, siz shifokor bilan maslahatlashingiz kerak. Fiziologik omillar tufayli glikemiyaning qisqa muddatli o'sishi davolanishni talab qilmaydi. Dori vositalari keltirib chiqaradigan giperglikemiya bo'lsa, qo'zg'atuvchi dorini bekor qilish, shuningdek uni almashtirish uchun ushbu preparatni buyurgan mutaxassis bilan maslahatlashish kerak.

Bir qator hollarda glikemiyaning normallashtirish uchun asosiy kasallikning malakali terapiyasi yetarli (tireostatik vositalar, steroidogenez ingibitorlari, somatostatin analoglari). Patologik giperglikemiya bilan og'riqan bemorlarni davolash uchun quyidagi choralar qo'llaniladi:

Parhez. Kam uglevodli dietaga rioya qilish giperglikemiyaning muvaffaqiyatli tuzatishning asosiy shartlaridan biridir. Avvalo, oson hazm bo'ladigan uglevodlar cheklash zarur – shokolad, xamir ovqatlar, kekslar. To'liq donlar (grechka, jo'xori uni) afzallik beriladi.

Jismoniy mashqlar. Har xil jismoniy mashqlarni muntazam ravishda bajarish tufayli mushaklar tomonidan glyukozadan foydalanish ko'payadi, bu esa glikemiyaning kamaytirishga imkon beradi.

Insulin terapiyasi. Insulin in'ektsiyalari 1-toifa diabet bilan og'rigan barcha bemorlar va homiladorlik diabeti bo'lgan homilador ayollar uchun qo'llaniladi. Insulin 2-toifa diabetning dekompensatsiyasi uchun ham buyuriladi. Terapiyaning samaradorligi glyukozalangan gemoglobin (HbA1c) maqsadli ko'rsatkichlariga erishishdir.

Qandni kamaytiradigan vositalar. II turdagi qandli diabetda, shuningdek, boshqa endokrinopatiyalardan kelib chiqqan giperglikemiyada gipoglikemik dorilar – biguanidlar (metformin), sulfonilmochevina hosilalari (glibenklamid), DPP-4 ingibitorlari (vildagliptin) tanlanadi.

Xirurgik davo

Ba'zi hollarda giperglikemiya konservativ usullar bilan tuzatib bo'lmaydigan hollarda (masalan, morbid semizlik va II turdagi diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda) ular bariatrik jarrohlik – me'dani aylanib o'tish, rezektsiya qilish va oshqozonni bog'lash usullariga murojaat qilishadi. Ko'pgina endokrinopatiyalarni muvaffaqiyatli davolash uchun jarrohlik operatsiyasi talab qilinadi – tireotoksikoz uchun tiroidektomiya, akromegaliya uchun transnazal adenomektomiya, Kushing sindromi uchun ikki tomonlama adenalektomiya.

Prognoz

Patologik giperglikemiya juda noqulay prognostik omil hisoblanadi. Yuqori glyukoza darajasi hayot uchun xavfli bo'lgan o'tkir sharoitlarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin – giperosmolyar giperglikemik koma va laktat atsidoz. Giperglikemiya leykotsitlarning fagotsitar faolligini bloklaydi, natijada yuqumli kasalliklarga nisbatan sezuvchanlik kuchayadi.

Qon tomir devorlarining lipoproteinlari va endoteliyasining glikozillanishi tufayli uzoq muddatli giperglikemiya aterosklerozning rivojlanishini tezlashtiradi. Keyinchalik, bu yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining (o'tkir miokard infarkti, insult),

shuningdek surunkali buyrak yetishmovchiligi, ko'rishning yo'qolishi, ekstremitalarning gangrenasining erta rivojlanishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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